

THE THERMAL EXPANSION PROPERTIES OF SPIRAL CARBON
FIBER - COPPER COMPOSITE *

Wang Chengfu, Ying Meifang and Wei Guangxia
Hefei University of Technology
Hefei, China

ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the thermal expansion properties of copper-carbon fiber composites. The thermal expansion coefficient of composites depends effectively on the fiber arrangement. The decreasing order of thermal expansion coefficients in different arrangements of fiber is 1, unidirectional, 2, spiral, 3, bidirectional, and 4, random distribution of short carbon fiber. The thermal expansion properties of spiral carbon fiber-copper composite were analyzed in more detail. The results show that the "rule of mixture" for composites must be carefully applied.

KEYWORDS : Composites; Fiber; Matrix, Copper.

1. INTRODUCTION

Copper-carbon fiber composites possess both the properties of copper and carbon fiber, i. e., excellent electrical, thermal conductivities and a small thermal expansion coefficient. The properties of these copper-carbon fiber composites can be adjusted not only by changing the volume fraction, but also the distribution and arrangement of carbon fibers. Composite with random distribution of carbon fibers has an isotropic thermal expansion coefficient. A bidirectional fiber arrangement composite has approximately isotropic thermal expansion coefficient in the horizontal, it is suitable to be the supporting electrode with the silicon wafer in power semi-conductor connecting devices⁽¹⁾. "Rule of mixture" for composites can be applied correctly to unidirectional arrangement of fibers, but it must be carefully used in some complicated situation. In this paper some special form of fiber arrangement of composite materials will be studied to discover the exact distinction between the calcu-
* Support by "NSFC"

lated results from the "Rule of mixture" and the experimental results of thermal expansion coefficients.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The Polyacrylonitrile(PAN) based carbon fibers are used in this work having a diameter of $7\mu\text{m}$. The ultimate tensile strength is about 2500MPa. Continuous electroplating technique of carbon fibers is adopted to produce a uniform thin copper coated film on the surface of the carbon fibers. The plated fibers are semiautomatically arranged in the spiral form shown in Figure 1 with a special winding equipment. Pieces of the composite specimen are hot pressed in an atmosphere of hydrogen at a temperature of $780\text{--}800^\circ\text{C}$ under a pressure of $25 \times 10^7 \text{ N/M}^2$ (2) presserving for 30min.

Figure 1. Winded fibers in spiral form

The average linear thermal expansion coefficient of the copper-carbon fiber composites in the range from room temperature to 200°C are measured with a quartz differential dilatometer. The size of the specimen of the spirally arranged composite is 30mm in diameter, 4mm thick.

3. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the typical microstructures of the copper-30% carbon fiber composite in spiral arrangement.

Table 1 shows the thermal expansion coefficient of spiral carbon fiber-copper composites. There are some data dispersion in different detective directions.

Table 2 shows the comparison of the thermal expansion coefficient of copper-carbon fiber composites in different fiber arrangement form. The effective-

ess of fiber arrangements in reducing the thermal expansion coefficient is in the decreasing order of 1. unidirectional, 2, spiral, 3, bidirectional and 4, random distribution of short carbon fiber.

Figure 2. The microstructure of spiral carbon fiber-copper composite ($V_f = 30\%$)

TABLE 1

The Thermal Expansion Coefficients of Spiral Carbon Fiber/Copper Composites ($V_f = 30\%$)

Thermal Expansion Coefficient	Temperature °C		
	20 - 50	20 - 80	20 - 120
$\alpha \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$	5.90	6.40	7.00

TABLE 2

The Thermal Expansion Coefficients of Copper/Carbon Fiber Composites at Different Fiber Arrangement

Thermal Expansion Coefficient	Arrangement Form				
	Unidirection		Spiral	Bidirectional	Short
	Tranverse	Longitudinal			
$\alpha \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$	14.60	3.76	5.65	6.28	8.80

4. DISCUSSION

The thermal expansion coefficient of composite along the longitudinal direction of fiber arrangement (α_{c1}) is determined mainly to carbon fiber, and

that in the direction perpendicular to it (α_{ct}) is determined to the metal matrix. According to the normal "Rule of mixture" the thermal expansion coefficients of composites can be calculated through the following formula :

$$\alpha_{cl} = \frac{\alpha_f E_f V_f + \alpha_m E_m (1 - V_f)}{E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f)}$$

$$\alpha_{ct} = \alpha_f V_f + \alpha_m (1 - V_f)$$

where

- α_f thermal expansion coefficient of fiber
- α_m thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix
- E_f young's modules of the fiber
- E_m young's modules of the matrix
- V_f volume fraction of fibers in composite,

when $V_f = 30\%$, the theoretical thermal coefficient α_{cl} is equal to $7.6 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ and α_{ct} is equal to $13.8 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$, only α_{ct} is coordinative with the experiments in table 2. The theoretical results are not agreement with experimental results of table 1 and table 2. The "Rule of mixture" must be under correction.

It is especially interesting when the arrangement of carbon fiber in spiral form, in this situation the detective directions of expansion coefficients are also perpendicular to the direction of carbon fibers, but the coefficient α_s is lower than α_{ct} . The main difference between these two arrangement forms is due to the continue and discontinue distribution of carbon fiber. The expansion of matrix copper is restricted by the closely arranged continuing spiral carbon fibers.

5. CONCLUSION

- 5.1 The average linear thermal expansion coefficients of the composite in the range from room temperature to 200°C are in the same level.
- 5.2 The effectiveness of fiber arrangement in reducing the thermal expansion coefficient is in the decreasing order 1) Unidirectional, 2) Spiral, 3) Bidirectional, 4) Short fiber in random distribution.
- 5.3 The thermal expansion coefficient of composite is not only dependent to the elastic modules and volume fraction of carbon fiber, but also the arrangement form of carbon fiber. "Rule of mixture" must be carefully applied.

6. REFERENCES

1. KEIICHI KUNYA, HIDEO ARAKAWA, TSUNEYUKI KANAI and TOMIO YASUDA, IEEE Transaction on Components, Hybrids and Manufacturing Technology, CHMT, 4, 1983.

2. C. Wang, M. Ying and Z. Wang, Proceeding of the 6th ICCM and ECCM, Elsevier applied science, London, 1987, pp. 2. 441.
3. J. R. Strife and K. M. Prewo, J. Comp. Mat 13, 10, 1979.

